

Subject:

Psychology

Title:

**The Impact of Social Media on Adolescent Mental Health:
A Literature Review**

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Abstract:

Social media plays a significant role in adolescent life, impacting mental health both positively and negatively. While platforms offer opportunities for peer support, self-expression, and identity formation, they also contribute to issues such as anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, body image concerns, sleep disruption, and cyberbullying. Social comparison often leads to negative self-perception, with adolescents feeling pressure to meet unrealistic standards. Cyberbullying and social media addiction further exacerbate psychological distress, and excessive use disrupts sleep patterns, affecting overall well-being. Despite these challenges, social media can foster social connectedness and emotional support. Interventions like digital literacy education and usage limits are essential to address its adverse effects. However, the relationship between social media and adolescent mental health is complex and requires more research. Future studies should focus on strategies that balance social media use to support positive mental health outcomes for adolescents.

Keywords:

Social media, adolescent mental health, anxiety, depression, self-esteem, body image, cyberbullying, sleep disruption, social comparison, digital literacy, and social media addiction.

Introduction

In recent years, social media has become an integral part of the daily lives of adolescents, profoundly influencing their mental health. Platforms like Instagram, TikTok, Snapchat, and Facebook have transformed how adolescents interact, communicate, and perceive themselves. While social media provides numerous opportunities for socialisation, information sharing, and self-expression, growing concerns have emerged about its adverse effects on mental health. This literature review explores how social media impacts adolescent mental health, including both positive and negative effects. Key areas such as anxiety, depression, self-esteem, and sleep disruption are examined. It also underscores the crucial role of parents, educators, and mental health professionals in guiding adolescents' social media usage and delivering critical support and intervention.

Positive Impacts of Social Media on Adolescents

Despite the negative connotations often associated with social media, research has shown several positive effects on adolescent mental health, such as facilitating peer support and promoting self-expression.

1. Peer Support and Connectedness: Adolescents often use social media for emotional support, sharing experiences and seeking peer encouragement. Valkenburg and Peter (2009) highlight how social media fosters online relationships that reduce loneliness and promote a sense of belonging. Allen et al. (2014) highlight social media's dual role, enhancing social connectedness through meaningful peer interactions while posing risks like overuse and mental health challenges, requiring careful management for adolescent well-being.

2. Self-Expression and Identity Formation: Social media plays a vital role in adolescent self-expression and identity formation. Boyd (2014) notes, teens use these platforms to explore different aspects

of their identity, which helps build confidence and self-awareness. By curating profiles and sharing content, adolescents' experiment with various facets of themselves, contributing to their development. Barker (2009) examines how gender, group identity, and collective self-esteem influence social media use among older adolescents. The study highlights that social networking sites help teens connect with peers, affirm their social roles, and enhance their collective self-esteem, making these platforms central to identity exploration and social engagement.

Ma and Leung (2019) examine how social media use motives affect self-disclosure and student engagement in university settings in *Computers & Education*. Their study shows that motives like seeking social interaction or information significantly influence how students share personal information and engage in learning. Students using social media primarily for social interaction tend to disclose more, leading to higher academic involvement. This highlights the importance of understanding social media use motives to improve educational practices. Educators can align these motives with engagement strategies to enhance student participation.

In their study published in the *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, *Manago, Graham, Greenfield, and Salimkhan (2008)* investigate self-presentation and gender differences on MySpace. They find that adolescents' online self-presentation strategies differ by gender. Girls focus on appearance and relationships, while boys emphasise social status and activities. These findings reveal that online self-presentation reflects broader social and developmental patterns, with gender playing a pivotal role in shaping how adolescents present themselves digitally. The study provides insights into the intersection of identity, gender, and online behaviour, showing how adolescents navigate social media to express their desired self-image. Both studies emphasise the role of social media in shaping academic engagement and self-identity.

Negative Impacts of Social Media on Adolescents

While social media offers benefits, research has highlighted significant adverse effects on mental health, including anxiety, depression, poor self-esteem, and sleep disruption.

Social media use has been linked to several mental health challenges among adolescents, notably anxiety, depression, decreased self-esteem, body image issues, sleep disruption, social comparison, envy, and cyberbullying. Research has shown that these issues can significantly impact the psychological well-being of young people.

1. Anxiety and Depression: Frequent social media use is associated with heightened levels of anxiety and depression in adolescents. Keles et al. (2020) conducted a systematic review that found a consistent relationship between excessive social media use and depressive symptoms, with factors such as cyberbullying, online harassment, and the unrealistic portrayal of life playing key roles. Adolescents often feel inadequate when comparing themselves to idealised images posted by peers or influencers, which leads to a rise in social anxiety.

2. Decreased Self-Esteem and Body Image Issues: One of the most significant adverse effects of social media on adolescents is its impact on self-esteem and body image. Tiggemann and Slater (2014) found that adolescent girls frequently exposed to appearance-focused content on platforms like Instagram and Snapchat experience higher levels of body dissatisfaction. The portrayal of idealised beauty standards on social media leads to negative self-evaluation, which can lower self-esteem, particularly among adolescent

girls. Fardouly et al. (2015) also demonstrated how social comparison through social media heightens body image concerns and increases the risk of eating disorders.

3. *Sleep Disruption*: Social media use can also disrupt sleep patterns, further affecting adolescent mental health. Levenson et al. (2016) found that adolescents who spend more time on social media experience poorer sleep quality, as nighttime notifications and messages delay sleep onset. Sleep disruption is a known risk factor for mental health issues like depression and anxiety.

4. *Social Comparison and Envy*: Social comparison and envy are also notable adverse effects of social media use among adolescents. Vogel et al. (2014) explored how social comparison on social media affects self-esteem and well-being. Published in the *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, the study found that frequent social comparisons on social media lead to envy and decreased self-worth. Adolescents often compare themselves to peers who present an idealised version of their lives, leading to inadequacy and dissatisfaction. This form of comparison is associated with mental health issues like anxiety, depression, and diminished life satisfaction.

5. *Cyberbullying*: Cyberbullying is another significant negative outcome of social media use. Kowalski et al. (2014) examined the prevalence and effects of cyberbullying in their study published in *Psychology of Violence*. Social media provides a platform for bullying that can be more pervasive and harmful than traditional bullying. The anonymity and broad reach of social media amplify the effects of bullying, resulting in severe emotional and psychological distress for victims. Cyberbullying can lead to increased feelings of fear, depression, and social withdrawal, all of which severely affect the mental health of adolescents.

6. *Social Media Addiction*: The concept of social media addiction has gained prominence as more adolescents become compulsively engaged with these platforms. According to Andreassen (2015), social media addiction is characterised by excessive concern about social media, a solid motivation to use it, and significant impairment in daily functioning due to overuse. Adolescents with high levels of social media addiction are more likely to report adverse mental health effects, including sadness and anxiety, as their dependence on these platforms increases.

Mitigating the Negative Effects of Social Media

Recognising the detrimental effects of social media on adolescents, several interventions can help mitigate these effects.

1. **Digital Literacy Education** Promoting digital literacy is crucial in helping adolescents navigate social media responsibly. According to Livingstone (2014), educating adolescents about the potential risks of social media, such as cyberbullying and the dangers of social comparison, can empower them to make informed decisions and regulate their online behaviour.
2. **Setting Limits on Usage** Parents and educators can play a pivotal role in regulating social media use by encouraging adolescents to set limits on screen time. Research by Twenge and Campbell (2018) suggests that limiting screen time to no more than two hours per day can significantly reduce the risk of developing depressive symptoms and anxiety.

Conclusion

The effect of social media on adolescents' mental health is multifaceted, with both positive and negative senses. While it provides opportunities for socialisation, peer support, and self-expression, its excessive use can lead to anxiety, sadness, body image issues, and sleep disruptions. Moreover, cyberbullying and social media addiction exacerbate the adverse effects on adolescent well-being. Interventions, such as digital literacy education and setting social media use limits, are essential in mitigating these adverse outcomes. Future research should explore more nuanced approaches to help adolescents balance their social media use in ways that promote mental well-being.

References

1. Andreassen, C. S. (2015). Online social network site addiction: A comprehensive review. *Current Addiction Reports*, 2(2), 175–184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40429-015-0056-9>
2. Boyd, D. (2014). *It is not straightforward: The social lives of networked teens*. Yale University Press.
3. Fardouly, J., Diedrichs, P. C., Vartanian, L. R., & Halliwell, E. (2015). Social comparisons on social media: The impact of Facebook on young women's body image concerns and mood. *Body Image*, pp. 13, 38–45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2014.12.002>
4. Keles, B., McCrae, N., & Grealish, A. (2020). A systematic review: The influence of social media on depression, anxiety, and psychological distress in adolescents. *International Journal of Adolescence and Youth*, 25(1), 79–93. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02673843.2019.1590851>
5. Levenson, J. C., Shensa, A., Sidani, J. E., Colditz, J. B., Primack, B. A. (2016). The association between social media use and sleep disturbance among young adults. *Preventive Medicine*, 85, 36–41. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2016.01.001>
6. Livingstone, S. (2014). Developing social media literacy: How children interpret risky opportunities on social network sites. *Communications*, 39(3), 283–303. <https://doi.org/10.1515/commun-2014-0113>
7. Tiggemann, M., & Slater, A. (2014). NetGirls: The Internet, Facebook, and body image concern in adolescent girls. *International Journal of Eating Disorders*, 47(6), 630–633. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eat.22343>
8. Twenge, J. M., & Campbell, W. K. (2018). Associations between screen time and lower psychological well-being among children and adolescents: Evidence from a population-based study. *Preventive Medicine Reports*, pp. 12, 271–283. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pmedr.2018.10.003>
9. Valkenburg, P. M. & Peter, J. (2009). Social consequences of the Internet for adolescents: A decade of research. *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 18(1), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-8721.2009.01595.x>
10. Barker, V. (2009). Older adolescents' motivations for social network site use: The influence of gender, group identity, and collective self-esteem. *CyberPsychology & Behaviour*, 12(2), 209–213. <https://doi.org/10.1089/cpb.2008.0228>
11. Allen, K. A., Ryan, T., Grey, D. L., McInerney, D. M., & Waters, L. (2014). Social media use and social connectedness in adolescents: The positives and the potential pitfalls. *Australian Educational and Developmental Psychologist*, 31(1), 18–31. <https://doi.org/10.1017/edp.2014.2>
12. Ma, J. L., & Leung, L. (2019). How motives for social media use and gratifications influence self-disclosure and student engagement in university learning: An empirical study in Hong Kong. *Computers & Education*, 130, 77-89. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2018.11.017>

13. Manago, A. M., Graham, M. B., Greenfield, P. M., & Salimkhan, G. (2008). Self-presentation and gender on MySpace. *Journal of Applied Developmental Psychology*, 29(6), 446–458. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appdev.2008.07.001>
14. Kowalski, R. M., Giumetti, G. W., Schroeder, A. N., & Wilson, S. K. (2014). Cyberbullying among college students: A review of the literature. *Psychology of Violence*, 4(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0035368>
15. Perloff, R. M. (2014). Social media effects on young women's body image concerns: theoretical perspectives and an agenda for research. *Media Psychology*, 17(1), 1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15213269.2013.831630>
16. Vogel, E. A., Rose, J. P., Roberts, L. R., & Eckles, K. (2014). Social comparison, social media, and self-esteem. *Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 33(10), 832–860. <https://doi.org/10.1521/jscp.2014.33.10.832>